

START- UP ENTREPRENEURS AND BUSINESS OPPORTUNITIES IN ODISHA

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Abstract— Odisha has a well natured economy system which focuses on the various areas like development of world class infrastructural, innovative as well as academic culture, sufficient training scope and opportunities for the essential skill and talent. The modern and creative ideas and business mindsets of today's youth would surely add worth to compete with the market perspectives nationally and globally. This paper aims to study the employment opportunities and the culture friendly environment for start-up entrepreneurship with the little skilled youth in the state of Odisha. Additionally, this paper attempts to discover the scope of entrepreneurship in the growing cities of Odisha. The objective of this paper is to understand the scope of the government policies to set up a favorable business platform for the sustainability of start- up entrepreneurship. It also seeks to explore the fundamental requirements in order to setup business environment through analyzing few literature reviews, collecting some secondary data and analyzing some data collected at the regional level.

Keywords— Entrepreneurship, company, business, start-ups, economy

INTRODUCTION

In today's competitive and progressive world, modern and innovative entrepreneurs are bringing new dimensions in growth and development of the economy. Since, innovation and creativity has the prospective to hack across all the aspects of human efforts, it is imperative to understand what compel this phenomena and how it can be managed in the best possible way in order to achieve utmost advantage.

Latest products and services as well as latest methods backed by sustainability, certainly can react to the requirements of customers at any time. Alternatively, it is argued that effective and efficient entrepreneurs are usually intensified towards a particular area in order to produce qualitative and creative products. Moreover, they could arrive at the desired goal due to acceptance of modern and latest technology and its implications. Consequently, efficiency spreads across which has an impact upon others to follow the method for setting up new business. It is advisable to reveal that entrepreneurship is nothing but planning and strategizing new product or service as well as executing in an organized process.

However, it has been noticed that new business opportunities appear by the entrepreneur and frequently, he comes up with a variety of thoughts and methods with a view to explore the opportunity. In this perspective, both entrepreneur as well as business form requires to be self-sustained. Nevertheless, for sustainability of the start-up business, the capability at a certain level of the desired outcome needs to be accessed and evaluated. Moreover, the task of the supportive environment plays an imperative role to enhance the entrepreneurial self-efficacy.

Presently, innovative and modern start-ups aim at disrupting the existing industries. But, existing business also depends on innovative skills and techniques for their survival. Innovation and creativity can turn interesting thoughts into viable start-up enterprises. A start up, these days, should come up with new ideas and thoughts to develop not only goods but also services that meet the changing taste and preferences.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Camp (2005), The entrepreneurial class provides leadership in resource change, innovation, technical progress and capital formation to produce new knowledge, new production techniques/possibilities, profits and economic growth. Conversely, entrepreneurial self-efficacy may be constituted of deliberation of the tasks that speak about the initiation and development of new ventures.

Mateja (2010) "Entrepreneurial self-efficacy is most excellent seen as a multidimensional creation made up of objective and control beliefs" and propositions for how the different dimensions will play a vital role during phases in the procedure of starting-up a new business. Self-efficacy creation has considerable instructive payoffs given that the entrepreneurship education should also focus on psycho-cognitive, social-cognitive and ethical perspectives of entrepreneurship.

Nuade (2011), It is highly important because in the absence standardised rules and regulation, entrepreneurship may result in undesirable social customs including corruption, crime, speculation and financial crisis and may worsen the vulnerability of people during natural disasters

Manocha (2012), Entrepreneurship is a creative and innovative response to the environment and an ability to recognize, initiate and exploit an economic opportunity. Presently, in the globalised world, sustainability or inventive idea based entrepreneurship requires renewing the process of stakeholders.

However, traditional or out-dated businessman doing routine-work has not been recognised as an entrepreneur.

Grant Thornton (2016), start-up business is an organization which is incorporated for three years or less, at a funding stage of second round. It is an entrepreneurial venture or a partnership which engages in development, production and distribution of new products or services, with a revenue of Rupees 25 crores, and formed with 50 employees or less.

OBJECTIVES OF THE PAPER

- 1- To study the scope of entrepreneurship in the state of Odisha.
- 2- To study the obstacles faced in start-ups in selected region in Cuttack district
- 3- To focus on scope of various opportunities and policies launched by the Government of Odisha to encourage start-ups entrepreneurs.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The paper is based on primary and secondary data. Primary Data have been collected by the help of pre- tested questionnaire, by applying stratified random sampling method. The study is also based on secondary data that has been collected from various publications at the state level. For the analysis, a sample size of 100 was taken, from which 50 respondents were available in the selected region in Cuttack district. Besides, some data were also collected from secondary sources. This paper is limited to the scope, obstacles and opportunities that appear in front of the start-up entrepreneurs.

START-UP ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN ODISHA

In Odisha, cities of Bhubaneswar, Cuttack and Puri have emerged as modern start up hubs. The Government of Odisha targets generating 0.4 million employment opportunities including enterprises in the micro, small & medium enterprises sector during financial year 2018-19. After cities like Bangalore, Hyderabad, Delhi NCR and Chennai, smaller cities like Bhubaneswar, Jaipur, Cochin and Indore are emerging as the modern and latest start-up hubs of India. During the last decade, the city of Bhubaneswar and Cuttack has seen extensive growth of start-ups. Some of the start-up business includes Mindfire Solutions, Tatwa Technologies, HelloDoctor24x7 Pvt. Ltd, Mediocor, AMOKart, etc.

One of the essential factors that make Bhubaneswar and Cuttack start-up hubs are the presence of world-class educational institutes that provide global exposure. Emergence of Information Technology giants like Infosys, Wipro and TCS in Bhubaneswar also acts as a channel for the speedy growth of start-up culture in these cities. Moreover, the youth of the city is enthusiastic, talented as well as innovative. Presently, the World Bank has ranked Bhubaneswar as one of the best place to do business in India. While interacting with the business entrepreneurs and motivators, it is found that Bhubaneswar is a great destination to maintain and validate customers.

OBSTACLES FACED BY START-UP ENTREPRENEURS

One of the most difficult barrier faced by the start-up entrepreneurs is the non-availability of adequate finance to start and carry out the operations. Banks also be uncertain to lend money without any adequate collateral mortgages or securities or guarantees and margin money which most of them are unable to provide. During the survey it was found that around 82 percent of the respondents said that high interest rates were the foremost impediment in getting start-up funds whereas 52 percent felt that no collaterals were the essential impediments, 40 percent said it was due to complex documentation procedure and 20 percent said it was due to strict credit scoring methodologies and other reasons.

Table- Obstacles faced by start-up entrepreneurs

Variables	Total Number of respondents
Social/Cultural Attitude	19
Access to Finance	46
Government regulations	21
Education, skill and training	22
Business support	31
Marketing/Promotion	17

From the sample survey, out of 50 respondents it was found that a majority of the respondents i.e., 46 respondents ranked access to finance as the first and foremost requirement where they faced problem to engage in the start-up. 21 respondents ranked government regulations as the barrier and 31 percent ranked business support as the important area of difficulty in the start-ups. This revealed that lack of adequate access to finance and business support were the most vital obstacles that the start-up entrepreneurs faced in the area.

START-UP ENTREPRENEURSHIP ENVIRONMENT

Entrepreneurship has the potential to transform the growth structure of the individual and result in prosperity and development of the economy as well. In Odisha, around 20,000 companies have registered under Micro Small Medium Enterprises department. The entrepreneurs are considerably contributing towards the development of society and economy in the forms of innovations and contributions of wealth. For effective start-up entrepreneurship environment, innovation as well as high growth entrepreneurship supportive mechanisms has played a major role in establishing start-up business. In this link, there are few areas where more work is needed for establishing start-up entrepreneurship hub in the cities like Bhubaneswar, Cuttack and Rourkela etc. The most important thing is that the entrepreneur should have innovative and creative ideas with precise growth trend with the support of state government for smooth functioning. The state of Odisha could play a major role as a regulator on regular basis, which is very imperative in the initial stage. Taking into consideration sustainable employment potential the Government of Odisha has formulated start up policy 2016, where the economy system is to be paying attention on innovation academic culture, well planned physical infrastructure and training for the requisite skills. In this innovative idea, the government is trying to deal with

effective participation of the educational institution to get involved during the progression of establishing start-up companies. The dense business environment in Odisha is focusing on IT, Healthcare and Sanitation, Agri Business and Food Processing, Tourism, and Garments, Chemical and Petrochemicals and Industries. However, the importance of these areas has been chosen based on the facts of Gross Domestic Product growth rate at 8.78 percent, which makes the state one of fastest growing state across the country and also estimated to grow at 12 percent by 2020. Abundant opportunities require favorable atmosphere and funding to grow in the long run.

SOME PROGRAMS TO ENCOURAGE START-UPS ENTREPRENEURS

The Government of Odisha has started various policies and programs to encourage start-up entrepreneurs in the formation of start-up business and towards the growth of economy of the region, state and nation. Few of them are:

1-Promotion of Dairy Entrepreneurship (PDE)

It has been projected to promote dairy entrepreneurs through provision of capital funding of 25 percent and 33.33 percent for general and reserved categories respectively, of the total project outlay for establishment of dairy units in the state. The main objectives are to promote modern dairy firms, upgrade traditional technology, handle milk on commercial scale, generate self-employment and provide infrastructure. Under this scheme, a total of 6,718 applications were sponsored out of which 1,657 applications were disbursed funds during the financial year 2016-17.

2- Odisha Youth Innovation Fund (OYIF)

Odisha Youth Innovation Fund aims to make Odisha an innovative society. It provides institutional support to innovation at starting level as well as outstanding traditional knowledge. An investment amount of Rupees 200 lakhs was funded by the State Government as well as the Corporate houses which included cost of management of funds, promotion and documentation of the program. The target group of OYIF is the entire youth mass of Odisha.

3- Ease of doing business

To ensure a comfortable business environment to the start-up entrepreneurs, a wide range of reforms along with technological interventions have been approved out by various departments of the State Government which includes the following:

- a- Go iplus: A web-enabled platform that is developed for mapping of industrial land and related infrastructure, raw materials and finished products of industries in the state of Odisha.
- b- e-Biz: An online web portal developed for submission of Common Application Form which serves as a single-stop shop for the business group of people in obtaining information.
- c- APAA: Automated Post Allotment Application is an online web portal developed with a view to facilitate online registration of application for any online payments and application tracking etc. for MSME sectors connected with IDCO.

- d- Invest Odisha- Mobile App and Website: This website and mobile application has been developed to provide vital information about the State's competitiveness, investment opportunities, focus sectors and incentives etc. to the prospective investors.

CONCLUSION

The state like Odisha, have improved business opportunity for start-up entrepreneurs and could draw the attention at the national as well as global perspectives. Proactive role of the government of Odisha would truly bring about new changes for smooth and hassle free services, setting up startup businesses towards effectiveness, access to funding in time and business support. However, still there are few areas which require giving a look, as it can be helpful to generate viable employment and business opportunity for start-up entrepreneurs, challenges or obstacles to meet the demand and supply of services as well as employment and lastly the capability of existing institutes within Odisha is to be measured.

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Annexure i
Questionnaire

Name-.....

Age-.....

Business/Occupation-.....

Location-.....

Q-1 Rank the following variables or obstacles faced in start-up business

Variables	Rank 1	Rank 2	Rank 3	Rank 4	Rank 5
Social/Cultural Attitude					
Access to Finance					
Government regulations					
Education, skill and training					
Business support					
Marketing/Promotion					

Q 2 Tick mark the reasons

- Access to finance-

High interest rates

Documentation

Collateral mortgages

Credit score

- Social/Cultural attitude

- Government regulation

- Business support from :

Family

Friends

Relatives

Others , Please specify.....